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Challenges and Outlooks of Forest Communities to Institutional Support in South-South, Nigeria

By

Olaleye S. M.

Review Article

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Olaleye S. M.

Department of Forestry and Wildlife Management, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, River State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's Email: sele.olaleye@yahoo.com, sele.warizeribe@uniport.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The forest, being naturally occurring vegetation, requires planning and management by diverse groups of stakeholders and managers for its preservation. This involves harnessing the rural people's interest in forest utilization as well as pitfalls of unsuccessful NGOs or extension officers. Inadequate sustainable planning and management initiatives accounts for the challenges and threats on the natural resources and human lives. There is need for checks and balances between challenges and outlooks at the people's disposal.

The challenges focuses on lack of sustainability for future generation, increased production, encouraging reforestation, preventing excessive silvicultural practice (pruning and pest control) and species adaption. Though active participatory and sustainable use may be best left to the rural dwellers in the forest whose needs and opinions are first considered but institutional support strengthens their efforts by enhancing their outlooks. Outlooks observed from the rural dwellers were lack of awareness of forest management activities, interest to plant trees, active age class (21–60yrs), local policy, highest monthly income of below ₦15,000, lack of proper storage and packaging, innovation, market price control, year round marketing, improvement of road network and small scale factory for institutional support. The way forward is integrated conservation, empowerment of the active age grades, gender roles, indigenous knowledge, study of the total economic value of sustainable forestry activities and strong partnership with forestry agencies or organizations.

However, evaluation and monitoring of local and institutional policies from time to time would create a sense of belonging for financial commitment, continual cooperation, poverty alleviation and sustainable management.

Keywords: Institutional support, Forest extension, Innovation, Forest exploitation, Active age class.

INTRODUCTION

The great potentials of African natural resources' contribution to the economic and social development are grossly undermined by the deforestation and degradation of the forest.

In Africa, deforestation occurred at the rate of 4 million hectares per annum from 1990-2000, 3.4 million hectares per annum from 2000-2010 (Chakravarty et al, 2014). The main reason of deforestation and degradation include: competition between human and other species, for the remaining ecological niches on land and in costal regions; failure in the working of the economic systems to reflect the time value of the environment;

Poverty pervades in the rural and remote areas and this has become both a cause and an outcome of declining supply of natural resources (Chanthalangsy, 2009);

Poor forest management policies, including unrestricted logging and excessive harvesting of fuel-wood contributed to environmental degradation (Eastnaugh, 2008).

In the drier areas of the tropics, fuelwood gathering can be a major cause of deforestation and degradation of the forest (Chakravarty et al, 2014).

These reasons of deforestation have direct (expansion of farming land, forest and other plantations, logging and fuel-wood, overgrazing, fires, mining, urbanization/industrialization and infra-structure, air pollution, wars and role of the militant and tourism) and indirect (colonialism, exploitation by industrialized countries, the debt burden, overpopulation and poverty, transmigration, and colonization schemes, land right, land tenure and inequitable land distribution and resources, economic causes-development/land conversion value, fiscal policies, markets, undervaluing the forest, corruption and political causes) causes in developing countries (Chakravarty et al, 2014).

Also, high annual population growth rates, large rural populations, accelerating urbanization and low per capital incomes do severely and collectively exert pressure on the forest for supply of fire wood, poles, food and medicine at non sustainable rates. These have resulted to increase in demand for resources, reduction of

biodiversity, inability to meet sustainable yield, climatic change of the globe and disrupted life pattern of many rural people (Whitmore, 1998; Olaseni, 2003; Olufemi, 2003).

Emphasizing the primordial importance of the forest to the Niger Delta, SPDC (2002) reiterated that apart from the crude oil and gas, distinct zones made up of faunal, terrestrial and aquatic species cover the area. In 1995, the World Bank stated that the full significance of the Niger Delta's biodiversity remains unknown because conservation units and species continue to be uncovered and major groups such as higher plants and birds remain unstudied in large areas.

Though the various values desired from the forest have been on the increase as far as development of other sectors is concerned, integrated management of the whole forest ecosystem must be embraced in partnership with other organizations if the numerous challenges facing the remaining forest communities will be mitigated.

Little success occurs when:

- Mixed feelings towards forest sustainability revolve around neglect, doubt, deceit and restrictions in utilization of allocated resources which has led to over-exploitation, free entrance and harassment of local communities.
- Conflicts involving forest land are not resolved in favour of either communities but are rather handed over to agencies that seem to have less practical approach to the issue of sustainability. This is because individuals vary in the readiness with which they express their views and indeed their interest in mangroves, opinion of depletion, support of reservation and adoption of new technology.
- The level of rapport and interaction between forest officers (especially Area Forest Officers) and notable community leaders in the state is low to allow for proper organization of the local people.

There is therefore the need for a planned strategy for integrating scientific and technical information with social requirements of the communities where the project is implemented. It requires approach from the grassroot instead of top-bottom where decision are merely passed down to the communities on what should be done and how and when (Okafor, 2003). Also, the importance of regeneration, tree cultivation studies and agroforestry intervention should be noted since many valuable exploited NTFPs species (*Rhizophora* spp., *Gnetum africanum*, *Iringia gabonensis* and *Dacryodes edulis*) are not within plantations (Okafor, 2003).

By virtue of mangrove proximity to the people, introducing meaningful strategies from the challenges and outlooks of past finding fulfills varied environmental and economic functions. To this end, technical needs that cover the financial, human and institutional resources, rural people involvement and links between rural people and government or NGOs must be identified.

The article tends to elicit the challenges and outlooks of forest community as well as the technical sustainability of these outlooks.

The South-South Region Critics

The South-South is a wetland region consisting of moist tropical lowland rain forest having coastal sediments, dominated by mangrove vegetation and located in the south southern part of Nigeria, and made up of six states (Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers). The bulk of this population resides in the commercial, industrial and business areas (urban) and the rural areas are mostly involved in fishing in the coast, logging in the forest and farming in the inland. This region has one of the highest oil deposits in the world. Though known for youth restiveness and marginalization due to this development, the difficult land terrain has resulted in poor infrastructural and political developments which have a part to play in NTFPs distribution and marketing. Recently the flood devastation has placed these areas into a more volatile zone. In addition, the GTZ study 2003 has reported that the greatest problem identified in the South-South is poverty, seventy percent of the people in the area are on poverty line and the poverty level in the region is well above African standards. More so, over two million youths are unemployed and they seem to have lost hope, faith and dignity in life, while 40% of the people are illiterates. Concerns for sustainable management of indigenous resources have been raised on integrated approaches in conservation, poverty alleviation and biological diversities.

Research Motivations for Enhancement of Rural Forestry

Rural households generally face deforestation, restricted land-use, large household, low availability of capital, price changes in marketable farm/forest produce and have little formal education. While indigenous knowledge about the environment and resource use may be high in rural areas, skill levels for dealing with external markets are generally low (Campbell and Luckert, 2002).

Key areas of priority in enhancing interest of rural people should therefore include:

- Production of multipurpose trees, fish and crops (Okafor, 2003).
- Research and training in crustacean culture in different growth medium.
- Advance vegetative propagation methods (Warizeribe, 2000).
- Improvement methods in unprocessed and processed NTFPs such as seeds and vegetables for seasoning and medicinal use.
- Provision of improved working tools in the production of commercial, household and fishing crafts (Warizeribe, 2013).
- Introduction of monitoring strategies for impact upgrading of established projects such as sawmills, small scale or cottage industry (Warizeribe, 2003; Adeyoju and Warizeribe, 2005).
- Development of markets for integrated uses and sales on food-, vegetable-, medicinal- and craft – related NTFPs which can significantly contribute to the household revenue and reduce environmental degradation (Warizeribe, 2008; Olaleye and Aiyeloja, 2013).

Action Frameworks for Agents of Rural Forest Management

The criteria for implementing plans and attacking challenges that will maximize efforts at conserving the renewable resources involve adoption of these action plans within rural people, within government/NGOs and between the rural people and government or NGOs. In India for instance, 7300 organizations are involved in forestry activities because local groups reflect the true needs, abilities and limitations of their community (Akinmayowa, 1996). The action plan or duties for each agent are thus.

❖ Rural people:

Adeyemo (2003) gives implementation plan for rural people below;

- Formation of objectives;
- Identification of resources;
- Formation of a coordinating organization;
- Organized and adequate funding;
- Encouragement of participation;
- Avoidance of undue domination and unhealthy competition.

❖ Within Government or NGOs /CBOs

- Capacity building and strengthening of centres as the level of involvement differs from community to community and NGO to NGO in their training, skills and finance availability to guide the fair use, access and control over the resources.
- Monitoring of NGOs and local institutions.
- Management information system that would authoritatively handle given standards for safety reasons and convenience.
- Sustainable livelihoods and management.
- Local, national and international policy that would meet especially the diverse demand for mangrove environment functions. This might become issues which will enter the mangrove forest policy process in problem definition and agenda setting, formulation, adoption and implementation. As time goes on with sustainability strategies in place, there will be need for evaluation of set and achieved goals (Olaleye and Agbeja, 2012a).

Promoting mangrove forestry in these states and national political agenda requires widespread public support that would influence the actions of politicians in any regime and the success of mangrove forestry would inspire many similar initiatives by communities and citizen groups throughout the state and nation. For instance, the removal of unwanted structures on the roadsides of the cities of Rivers State would encourage the introduction of Urban or Social Forestry schemes.

❖ **Between Rural People and Government or NGO**

According to DFID (2002) implementation plan between rural people and government includes;

- Identification of natural, human, financial, physical and social resources.
- Manipulation of vulnerabilities through institutional policies and processes.
- Management systems of livelihood strategies.
- Achievement of aspirations and sustainability of resources and assets for continuous provision of benefits and in areas requiring some special knowledge for initiation, passive involvement or facilitation and encouragement.

Challenges of Participation in Forestry Activities

Challenges observed in thirty communities of Akwa-Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta and Rivers State focused on the people and the forest. According to Warizeribe (2013) the forest of the South-South is still seen as a place of getting higher benefits such as cash needs from agricultural produce and NTFPs rather than a place of reservation. This is revealed in the people's lack of willingness to plant tree which in most cases responses are not impressive (Olaleye and Agbeja, 2012b). This is due to the fact that the following issues have not been inculcated into rural responsibility. Issues such as, Sustainability for future generation, Increased production, Encouraging reforestation, Preventing excessive silvicultural practice such as pruning, Pest and disease control, Species study and adaption were hard to find in these areas (Wahua and Olaleye, 2013).

This indicates that the people have accepted the fact that depletion is gradually taking the place unaware. The implication is that the level of knowledge of environmental issues: opinion of depletion, ignorance of the state of the forest and geographical terrain were enough to create change or awareness.

Outside the forest, marketing of produce reveals its own challenges such as the distance and poor means of transportation, lack of market information, prices of produce in the rural areas are low compared to urban prices, high levies on transportation and poor road network for those who insist on selling in urban areas, storage and safety of waterways.

These later challenges were indicators of poverty and inability to value their produces properly especially the non-timber forest produce (Olaleye and Agbeja, 2011). This implies that most people would not adopt the new technology from agencies sent for reservation effort as well as doubts hinged on local policy practiced in the area, instability of these policies, availability of market for their products and the tree planting effectiveness which throws a challenge to sustainable planners. These should opt for reformation of stringent policies that would create awareness to environmental change and its mitigation.

Rural Participatory Outlooks in Forestry Activities

Participatory outlooks in forestry are necessary tool for sustainable management, since it serves as a reference point for continuous intervention, assessment and positive manipulation of set objectives. The outlook options were summary of situations that lead to the challenges of the forest, rural people and government or non-governmental organization.

Therefore, the outlook options as reported by Warizeribe (2013) were a summary of the state of the forest, rural people and government or non-governmental organization. The investigation expresses the highest occurring forestry activities that would serve as major factors for extension planners and institutional support. The findings were awareness of forest management activities, interest to plant trees, gender role, active age class (21 – 60yrs), local policy, highest monthly income of below ₦15,000, lack of proper storage and packaging, innovation, market price control, year round marketing and improvement of road network were remarkable outlooks for institutional support. In addition, the types of cottage enterprises (small scale factories) identified were fuel-wood gathering, basket industry/household craft, fishing craft, carving industry, weaving industry, poles trading, wild fruit trading, medicinal plant trading, bush bar, trade in wild vegetables, seedling production, charcoal production, oil palm production, rubber production, palm wine and local gin production (Larinde, 2003; Warizeribe, 2013).

A critical observation of a particular rural situation would involve the adjustment of every concerned and intending sectors in achieving reduced income and poverty increase, insufficient empowerment and vegetation conservation, increased depletion of fishes and deforestation, pollution, improper sustainable use of natural resources and insufficient food security.

The Way Forward for Institutional Forestry Support

Collaboration among different institutional and social interactions and local resources users in integrated conservation and development participatory approach is recently being recognized. Warizeribe (2008) highlights the approaches thus:

- Integrated conservation, such that have a good understanding of the suitable agroforestry processes to be introduced is necessary to reduce the cost of project execution.
 - Economically empowering the active age grades and gender roles that are capable of successfully accomplishing the set objectives as it relates to the forest.
 - Indigenous knowledge could be harnessed in some areas, thereby reducing the support or withdrawal of support to avoid perceived pitfalls. This would increase the interest of the rural people (especially Women) as efforts are intensified in new improved initiatives (Olaleye and Omokhua, 2012).
 - The study of the total economic value of sustainable forestry activities for long-term cooperation needs to be assessed with incentives. This would mean knowing their financial commitment to the community or private organization membership and families associated with participation in forestry.
 - The continuous entertainment of occasional activities by forest extension workers;
 - Strong partnership with forestry agencies or organizations heightens the administration of sustainable processes. This was because their implementations require continuous consultation and dialogue with the people as their commitments are at different levels, opinions and interest.
- In addition, Ekeke (2003) also reported that community forestry and poverty reduction in the Niger Delta mangroves were possible strategies for rural development.

Technical Mitigation of Outlooks

Maintaining these multiple functions and service is another enormous challenge to all collaborators. The various outlooks to participation have also broadened the scope for potential recreation and tourism. Involvement of technical advisers (expertise) from government, non-governmental organizations and researchers (universities and institutes) to establish emerging strategies have come to stay but must be sustained.

Improvement of indigenous techniques in collection, processing and storage of perishable products up to the national and international standard such that there is a level of competition and certification awareness from the local areas have in no doubt sustained products.

The type of security outfit plays an important role here due to the youth restiveness, disenchantment by the indigenes and political instability. In this regards, employing the services of the law enforcement agents to implement technical policies on multiple land use, product valuation and climate change mitigation in the Rivers State. This becomes a non-use-conservation participatory approach to achieving forest sustainability, protection of lives, properties and food security.

CONCLUSION

South-South Nigeria, a people saddled with a lot of responsibilities should not base their institutional support on democratic processes since a change in regime would bring about misappropriation of priority in financing of the forestry sector, rather on integrated participatory strategies and local people intervention. Participatory outlook materials aid effective networking in action plans, show greater interest and willingness and give access to increased rewards from the forest and community.

Technically, the forestry training institutions should have a complete re-orientation in dealing with community intruders or trespassers on forest estate where daily means of livelihood are derived and respond made to the presented challenges.

Regardless of mangrove forest ecological setting, agroforestry activities that would encourage tree and pond domestication would be a welcoming initiatives to the people.

Evaluation of local and institutional policies from time to time creates a sense of belonging for continual cooperation and sustainable management.

Fortunately, to attain active sustainable management sometimes may be best left to the rural dwellers whose needs, opinions and preferences are first considered; though in other cases professionals may wish to do the work themselves.

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